

21NRM06 EMC-STD

D8: Good practice guide detailing i) the APD calibration method and the associated sources of uncertainty ii) methods for interpreting and presenting the APD calibration results

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Abbreviations

APD	Amplitude Probability Distribution
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
CCDF	Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function
RF	Radio Frequency
A/D	Analog to Digital converter
CW	Continuous wave – Sine wave
EUT	Equipment under test
EMI	Electromagnetic interference
RBW	Resolution Bandwidth
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
WGN	White Gaussian Noise
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Model
CDF	Cumulative distribution function
PDF	Probability density function

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1. Introduction

This report summarises activities A4.4.1, A4.4.2, A4.4.3 and A4.4.4 of the EMC-STD project. The mentioned activities aim to develop a calibration procedure to calibrate the APD measurement function of EMI measuring receivers. Two complementary APD calibration methods were developed to meet the APD calibration requirements specified in CISPR 16-1-1:2019 [1]. These two calibration approaches, labelled "deterministic" and "statistical," are described in detail in Section 2, including the actual calibration procedure. Examples of the uncertainty budget calculation are provided. The performance results of these calibration methods are in Section 3.

1.1 Definition of APD function

CISPR 16-1-1:2019 [1] defines the APD of the measured disturbance as the cumulative distribution of the probability of time that the amplitude of the disturbance exceeds a specified level. The APD can be measured at the output of the envelope detector or at the outputs of succeeding circuits in an RF measuring receiver. Usually, an APD measurement is carried out at a fixed frequency, and the standard defines the frequency range from 1 GHz to 18 GHz.

Formally, the APD function can be defined as follows. Let us suppose that we have a signal $x(t)$, the corresponding APD measuring function $APD(x_{th})$ returns the probability that the instantaneous amplitude of the envelope of a signal $x_{env}(t)$, is greater than a previously specified threshold, $x_{th}(t)$. The relation can be expressed in an equation as:

$$APD(x_{th}) = P(x_{env}(t) > x_{th}). \quad (1)$$

The envelope of the signal $x_{env}(t)$ is obtained through the in-phase and quadrature components of the down-converted signal. The in-phase component is $x_i(t)$ and the quadrature component is $x_q(t)$. The envelope can then be defined as:

$$x_{env}(t) = \sqrt{x_i^2(t) + x_q^2(t)}. \quad (2)$$

The APD function quantifies the time during which the measured envelope of an interfering signal exceeds a given level. If X_{env} is defined as a random variable of amplitudes x , with a probability density function $f_{x_{env}}(x)$, distributed according to the instantaneous values of $x_{env}(t)$, then the APD of X_{env} , written as $APD_{x_{env}}(x)$ can be defined as:

$$APD_{x_{env}}(x) = 1 - F_{x_{env}}(x) \quad (3)$$

$F_{x_{env}}(x)$ is the cumulative distribution function of X_{env} , defined as:

$$f_{x_{env}} = \frac{dF_{x_{env}}(x)}{dx} \quad (4)$$

This definition means that measuring the APD requires estimating the $f_{x_{env}}(x)$ of measured emissions, or, in our case, the reference calibration signal. In practice, the most basic method for estimation is the histogram of relative frequencies of occurrence [2]. An alternative approach was also proposed as part of the EMC-STD project, namely the Kernel Density Estimation method [3]. The result of APD measurement is a graph. The horizontal axis displays the signal amplitude thresholds in logarithmic units. The vertical axis shows the probability that the signal amplitude exceeds the threshold specified on the horizontal axis.

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1.2 Calibration requirements for APD function according to CISPR 16-1-1:2019

CISPR 16-1-1:2019 prescribes several requirements that the APD measurement function must satisfy. The rationale for these requirements is described in Annex G of the same standard. The requirements that are subject to calibration are:

- 1) The amplitude dynamic range shall be greater than 60 dB.
- 2) The amplitude tolerance, including threshold-level-setting error, shall be better than ± 2.7 dB.
- 3) The minimum measurable probability shall be 10^{-7} .
- 4) The resolution of the pre-assigned amplitude levels shall be 0.25 dB at a minimum.

2. APD calibration methods and the associated uncertainty

The proposed calibration procedure has two stages, one based on deterministic and well-defined reference signals and a later stage where the APD output is evaluated with respect to pseudo-random signals of known and controllable statistical properties. The deterministic stage focuses on directly comparing the amplitudes and probability values of the APD measured at the receiver versus their respective expected values calculated from the reference signal characteristics. The statistical calibration stage compares the summary statistics extracted from the probability density functions of both the pseudo-random reference signals and the measured APD to obtain the APD calibration.

2.1 Deterministic calibration method

The deterministic calibration method consists of applying a known RF signal to an APD measuring device. This procedure aims to test the APD measuring device for amplitude accuracy better than ± 2.7 dB and probability accuracy, as well as to determine that the measured APD has a sufficient dynamic range of at least 60 dB. To achieve this, a reference signal is constructed from two known RF signals with a common time base. The first signal $s(t)$ has a power level L_1 and has a CW form. The second signal $w(t)$ has a power level L_2 and is pulse modulated. The level L_2 is at least 60 dB higher than L_1 . Signals $s(t)$ and $w(t)$ are combined in a dual-directional RF coupler and applied to the APD measuring device input. After combining $s(t)$ and $w(t)$, the resulting reference signal produces an APD that has a probability peak P_1 that corresponds to the signal with power level L_1 , and a right tail in the probability distribution whose probability amplitude P_2 is defined by the pulse modulation rate, or duty cycle, of $w(t)$ with power level L_2 . The probability P_2 is related to the width and period of the pulsed modulated signal with the following Eq. 5.

$$P_2 = \frac{\text{Width}}{\text{Period}} \tag{5}$$

Figure 1 - Diagram of deterministic APD calibration procedure.

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Fig. 1 shows a simplified diagram of the calibration procedure. Signals are measured with RF power sensors and adjusted to the desired level before being applied to the APD measuring receiver input. The resulting APD is measured, and the results are compared with the reference values determined from RF power level measurements and the pulse modulation rate. To estimate the final measurement uncertainty, one needs to evaluate the uncertainties in the reference values and in the APD measurement. The general procedure is described in the following subsections.

2.1.1 RF Power level calibration and its uncertainty

Before performing the APD calibration on the measuring receiver under calibration, the RF power levels are determined with an RF power sensor. Both RF signal generators should be turned on at least one hour before the measurements to ensure they are adequately warmed up. The warm-up period ensures that the set RF power level is stable and does not fluctuate. The stability of the set power level should be verified with an RF power sensor. The generators also share a common time base source. In Figure 2, the "RF Generator 1" provides the lower CW signal $s(t)$, and "RF Generator 2" provides the higher pulsed modulated signal $w(t)$ at the same frequency of interest.

Figure 2 - Setup for RF power level calibration

RF Generator 1 is connected to the coupler input port via a 30 dB attenuator. The attenuator is used to reduce the mismatch that would be caused by RF generator 1's output. RF Generator 2 is connected to the coupler's output coupled port. An additional attenuator is not required here since unwanted reflections are attenuated by a coupler's coupling constant.

The RF power sensor is connected to the coupler's output port, and a zero-compensation calibration is performed on it when both RF signal generators are off. After the zero compensation, RF Generator 1 is turned on, and the power at the coupler's output port is measured. The offset from the desired power level is recorded, and the generator's output level is adjusted accordingly. This process runs on a controlling computer as long as the measured offset is larger than, for example, 0.03 dB. When the process ends, the power level setting on RF Generator 1 is recorded and saved for later use. The same process is then applied with RF Generator 2 with pulsed modulation turned off (only the CW signal is present). The final power level setting on RF Generator 2 is recorded and saved.

The actual RF power level L_s present at the coupler's output port (L_1 and L_2) with its associated uncertainty is calculated with the model in (6). This represents a general model for RF power measurements performed with an RF power sensor. The final form of the equation depends on the specific power sensor's theory of operation. One should modify or adapt the equation to suit the specific power sensor being used. Every term in the equation is explained below.

$$L_s = \frac{(P_{disp} + k_{lin} + k_{res} + k_{zero} + k_{noise})}{CF + dCF} * M + (k_{REP}) \quad (6)$$

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P_{disp} – Power displayed by the power sensor

This value is calculated as the mean of several power sensor readings taken during Measurement. Its standard uncertainty is determined as the standard deviation of the mean of all readings used in its calculation. This contribution is assumed to follow a normal probability distribution.

k_{lin} – Correction factor due to power sensor linearity

The value of this correction is taken to be 0 W, with associated uncertainty obtained from the power sensor specifications, and confirmed through calibration of the power sensor. This contribution is assumed to have a rectangular probability distribution.

k_{res} – Correction factor due to power sensor reading resolution

This quantity corresponds to the least significant digit of the measured or displayed result. The correction is taken to be 0 W, with an associated uncertainty of \pm half the measurement resolution, assuming a rectangular probability distribution.

k_{zero} – Correction factor due to zero offset

The value of this correction is taken to be 0 W, with associated uncertainty obtained from the power sensor's specifications. This contribution is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution. Zero correction contribution is not considered if zero correction is made right before each Measurement, since the drift after compensation will be negligible.

k_{noise} – Correction factor due to noise

The value of this correction is taken to be 0 W, with associated uncertainty obtained from the power sensor's specifications for residual noise. This contribution is assumed to follow a normal probability distribution.

CF – Calibration factor of the power sensor

The value of the calibration factor is obtained from the power sensor's calibration certificate together with its associated uncertainty. This uncertainty is assumed to follow a normal probability distribution.

dCF – Drift of the power sensor calibration factor since last calibration

This value is taken to be 0 W with its associated uncertainty derived from the analysis of the most recent calibration certificates. This contribution is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution.

M – Mismatch factor of the system

The average value of the mismatch factor of the system is 1, with the upper and lower bounds defined by Eq.(7). This contribution is assumed to follow a U-shaped probability distribution. The magnitude of these bounds is determined from the measured reflection coefficient of the power sensor Γ , and the coupler's output port parameter $S_{22Coupler}$ multiplied by the measured uncertainty $U(\Gamma_{meas}, S_{22Coupler})$ as seen in (8) and (9).

$$M = 1 \pm 2|\Gamma_{PowerSensor}| |S_{22Coupler}| \quad (7)$$

$$|\Gamma_{PowerSensor}| = \sqrt{|\Gamma_{meas}|^2 U(|\Gamma_{meas}|)^2} \quad (8)$$

$$|S_{22Coupler}| = \sqrt{|S_{22Coupler}|^2 U(|S_{22Coupler}|)^2} \quad (9)$$

k_{REP} – Correction factor due to RF level repeatability in pulse modulation mode

The RF power level of the pulsed-modulated signal is determined when modulation is turned off and only a CW signal is present. When pulse modulation is enabled, the RF power level may differ from the value measured in CW mode. The correction value is taken to be 0 W. The associated uncertainty is obtained from the specifications of the RF signal generator. This contribution is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution. Alternatively, this uncertainty contribution can be drawn with an oscilloscope. The RF generator is connected to the oscilloscope's input, and the signal level is measured in both CW and pulse modulation modes. The difference between the two measurements is taken as an estimate of this uncertainty contribution. The absolute accuracy of the oscilloscope can be neglected since only the difference in the measured signal levels is relevant. This uncertainty contribution is only applied to the pulse-modulated signal, L_2 .

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2.1.2 Probability level of the reference signal L_2 and its uncertainty

The measured probability P_2 of a signal level L_2 is related to the pulse modulation width and period, along with its associated uncertainty, as expressed by Eq. 10. This equation applies to periodic signals. The uncertainty is also estimated using the same equation. It depends on the pulse parameter specifications of the RF signal generator used. Most modern RF signal generators implement pulse modulation using an internal function generator combined with an electronic switching mechanism. Typically, the frequency and timing parameters are specified to have the same nominal accuracy as the RF signal generator's time base. However, practical measurements often reveal discrepancies from these stated specifications. Consequently, independent calibration of the internal function generator is recommended to verify its compliance with the manufacturer's stated performance. An example of a combination of signals $s(t)$ and $w(t)$ can be seen in Fig. 3. The period of the L_2 signal is 1s and width is $0.1\mu\text{s}$. This signal will produce a right tail in the measured APD with $P_2 = 10^{-6}$.

$$P_2 = \frac{\text{Width} + k_{wspecs}}{\text{Period} + k_{pspecs}} \quad (10)$$

Figure 3 - Pulse modulated RF signal with a period of 1 s and width of $0.1\mu\text{s}$.

k_{wspecs} – Correction factor due to width uncertainty

The value is taken to be 0 s, with associated uncertainty obtained from specifications or measured during the signal generator's calibration. This contribution is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution.

k_{pspecs} – Correction factor due to period uncertainty

The value is taken to be 0 s, with associated uncertainty obtained from specifications or measured during the signal generator's calibration. This contribution is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution.

To achieve low probability levels, the pulse-modulated signal's width must be reduced or its period increased. However, achieving arbitrarily low probability levels is not feasible because the minimum achievable pulse width is limited to several tens of nanoseconds. In such cases, a single pulse can be employed. The measured probability should then correspond to the ratio between the pulse width generated by the RF generator and the total measurement duration, as shown in (11). The only significant source of uncertainty arises from the specified pulse width. Since the measuring receiver is under calibration, and both signals determine the total measurement time, and they share a common time base, the uncertainty is solely associated with the pulse width. This uncertainty arises from the internal function generator of the RF source, where small deviations may occur relative to the time base.

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$$P_2 = \frac{Width + k_{wspecs}}{T_{meas}} \quad (11)$$

k_{wspecs} – Correction factor due to width accuracy

The value is taken to be 0 s, with the associated uncertainty obtained from specifications or measured during the signal generator's calibration. The contribution is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution.

Another potential source of uncertainty that may affect the reference signal probability level is the rise time of the pulse modulation. However, the rise time of modern RF signal generators is typically less than 10 ns, which is significantly shorter than the achievable pulse modulation width. Therefore, its influence on overall uncertainty is negligible.

2.1.3 Combined reference signal

The reference calibration signal consists of a sum or superposition of signals $s(t)$ and $w(t)$. An ideal reference can be seen in Fig. 4. The signal $s(t)$ from the first RF signal generator has a power level $L_1 = 52$ dB μ V, set via an iterative RF power sensor measurement. The higher pulse modulated signal $w(t)$ from the second RF Generator 2 has a power level $L_2 = 107$ dB μ V, which was also set with an RF power sensor as described in the previous chapter. The combination produces a reference APD distribution in Figure 5. The red line in the figure is the result of the power level signal L_1 w, which is constantly present; therefore, its probability is equal to $P_1 = 1$. The signal $w(t)$ has a higher power level L_2 and is pulse modulated so that the ratio of pulse modulation width to the period is equal to $P_2 = 10^{-6}$, which results in the right tail in the APD distribution, marked with a blue line.

Figure 4 - Ideal reference signal

2.1.4 Measurement of power level with APD measuring function and the associated uncertainty

When the reference signal combination is characterised as described in the previous chapter, a measurement can be made on the receiver under calibration. The amplitudes that are measured by the measuring receiver APD function (L_x) are modelled by (12). The estimated uncertainty is also modelled with the same equation. All terms in the equation are described in detail below.

$$L_x = P_{meas} + k_{res} + k_{AL} + k_{FR} + k_{DL} + k_{RL} + k_{ATT} + k_M + k_{NOISE} \quad (12)$$

P_{meas} – Level displayed by the APD function

This value is taken from the APD measurement results for the receiver under calibration. If only one measurement run is performed, this uncertainty contribution can't be evaluated. Alternatively, if several

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measurements are conducted, this value is the mean amplitude across all measurements. This quantity has a standard uncertainty calculated as the standard deviation of the mean of all readings used in its calculation. This contribution is assumed to follow a normal probability distribution.

k_{res} – Correction due to the resolution of the reading

This quantity corresponds to the least significant digit of the displayed amplitude level result. The correction is estimated to be 0 dB, with an associated uncertainty of \pm half the resolution. The uncertainty is assumed to have a rectangular probability distribution.

k_{AL} – Correction due to absolute accuracy specifications

The value of this correction is 0 dB. Associated uncertainty is estimated from the specifications. The uncertainty is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution.

k_{FR} – Correction due to the frequency response

The value of this correction is 0 dB. The associated uncertainty is estimated from the specifications. The uncertainty is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution. In general, the measuring receiver's specifications will cover the entire frequency range of use. This uncertainty contribution can be eliminated if the receiver's absolute error is calibrated at the same frequency as the APD calibration; in that case, the measured value serves as the correction for absolute accuracy.

k_{DL} – Correction due to display linearity

The value of this correction is 0 dB. The associated uncertainty is estimated from the specifications. The uncertainty is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution.

k_{ATT} – Correction due to input attenuator switching

The value of this correction is 0 dB. The associated uncertainty is estimated from the specifications. The uncertainty is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution. If the attenuator setting matches the specified absolute and frequency response levels, then this uncertainty can be reduced to 0 dB.

k_{RL} – Correction due to reference level setting

The value of this correction is 0 dB. The associated uncertainty is estimated from the specifications. The uncertainty is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution. If the reference level setting matches the specified absolute and frequency response levels, then this uncertainty is 0 dB.

k_M – Correction due to mismatch

The value of this correction is 0 dB. The associated uncertainty is estimated from the reflection coefficient of the measuring receiver and coupler's output port via the procedure described in Eq. 7-9, where the measuring receiver input reflection coefficient substitutes the power sensor's reflection coefficient.

k_{NOISE} – Correction due to uncertainty contribution from the receiver's noise floor

The value of this correction is 0 dB. The corresponding uncertainty cannot be directly derived from the measuring receiver's specifications. Although the datasheet typically specifies the instrument's noise floor, it does not describe the cumulative noise floor contribution that affects the APD measurement. This contribution can be significant because APD measurements or calibrations are typically performed with a 1 MHz resolution bandwidth, where the noise level may be comparable to that of the lower power level signal $s(t)$. To evaluate this uncertainty, the receiver input should be terminated with a precision 50 Ω impedance-matched RF load, and several APD measurements should be performed. The average of these readings represents the effective noise floor of the APD measurement. An example of such an average is shown in Fig. 5. The uncertainty associated with noise is determined by calculating the power ratio between the measured APD of the reference signal and the measured APD noise floor. This ratio defines the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The upper and lower limits of this ratio can be estimated using (13).

$$NOISE = 20 \log_{10} \left(1 \pm \left(\frac{1}{10^{SNR_{dB}}} \right) \right) \tag{13}$$

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The difference in the upper and lower bounds is then taken as the associated uncertainty. The uncertainty is assumed to follow a rectangular probability distribution. Care should be taken to ensure that the lower-power-level signal $s(t)$ is sufficiently above the noise floor.

Figure 5 - APD measurement of average noise contribution with terminated input.

2.1.5 Measurement of probability level with APD measuring function and the associated uncertainty

The probabilities measured by the EUT's APD function (P_X) are modelled using Eq. 14. The estimated uncertainty is also modelled with the same equation. All terms in the equation are described in detail below.

$$P_X = P_{X_MEAS} + k_{res} \tag{14}$$

P_{X_MEAS} – Probability level displayed on EUT

This value is taken from the APD displayed results. This value has no associated uncertainty.

k_{res} - Correction due to the sampling resolution of the EUT

The value of this correction is 0. Associated uncertainty is estimated from the sampling resolution of the applied APD function. The resolution is calculated from the number of samples and the measurement time by the following equation.

$$U(k_{res}) = \frac{T_{meas}}{N_{samples}} \frac{1}{1s} \tag{15}$$

2.1.6 Uncertainty propagation and combined uncertainty

The preceding subsections present the error models and identify the corresponding sources of measurement uncertainty. These models have been formulated to be as general as possible, enabling their application in any calibration laboratory capable of performing a deterministic calibration procedure for the APD function. To derive a final uncertainty, the individual uncertainty components from each model must be propagated through the model in accordance with European Accreditation guidelines [4]. The process begins by obtaining uncertainty estimates for all relevant parameters, using either instrument specifications, calibration certificate data, or the estimation procedures described earlier. Each uncertainty must then be expressed as a normal probability distribution and combined using linear error propagation methods. Finally, the combined standard uncertainty is multiplied by an appropriate coverage factor to produce the expanded uncertainty corresponding to a 95% confidence level. A detailed description of each step is provided in [4].

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All experimental work for the deterministic calibration approach was done with the following equipment:

- RF signal generator Keysight MXG Vector Signal Generator N5182B
- RF signal generator Keysight MXG Analog Signal Generator N5183B
- RF Dual-directional coupler HP 778D
- RF Power sensor Rohde & Schwarz NRP18T
- RF Power sensor HP 8484A with accompanying power meter HP EPM E4419A

With the above equipment, the uncertainty of the reference signal in terms of signal power level ranges from ± 0.05 dB to ± 0.09 dB, depending on the power level being measured. The uncertainty in the measured APD of the EUT, of course, depends on its specifications. Typically, with current-generation benchtop measuring receivers, uncertainties in the measured APD power range from 1.3 dB to 1.9 dB. These uncertainties allow us to confirm that the receiver complies with the CISPR 16-1-1 standard, since the error tolerance defined therein is 2.7 dB.

The uncertainties of reference signals, in terms of probability, depend on the specifications of the RF signal generator used. With current benchtop generators, the uncertainty is in the order of 10^{-8} . The uncertainty in the measured probability levels for the EUT depends on the number of samples taken and the total measurement time. In experiments conducted within this project, uncertainties in the order of 10^{-7} were achieved. Such uncertainties are comparable to the lower probability levels required by the standard. It does not make sense to calibrate to such low-probability levels, since the calibration uncertainty will be too large relative to the calibrated value. As will be seen in a later section, the deterministic calibration technique will be limited in use to probabilities in the range of 10^{-6} .

2.1.7 Traceability of APD calibration

Traceability of the calibration procedure is maintained through an unbroken chain of calibrations linked to the fundamental international SI units. Within the deterministic calibration method, this traceability specifically supports the estimation of the APD reference signal and the associated uncertainty. RF power level measurements are traceable to international standards through calibrated power sensors. The frequency and time parameters of the employed RF signal generators are calibrated and traceable. In addition, the directional coupler is characterised using a vector network analyser calibrated with reference-traceable terminations to account for and quantify uncertainties arising from impedance mismatch.

2.2 Statistical calibration method

Figure 6 shows the procedure used to obtain the APD statistical calibration.

This procedure can be divided into 3 steps: firstly, the generation of pseudo-random pattern signals and their time-domain and APD measurements; secondly, the digital processing of the samples; and finally, the obtention of the statistical results that allow us to calibrate the APD.

The procedure starts with the generation of known-pattern pseudo-random signals WGN and GMM using an arbitrary waveform (AWG), $x(t)$, in baseband. Then $x(t)$ is captured with a real-time oscilloscope to extract the sampled signal digitally, $X[n]$, as shown in Figure 7. By performing this measurement in baseband, the limitations on calibration capabilities imposed by the Real-Time Oscilloscope's bandwidth can be overcome. Also, as the statistical properties of $x(t)$ are not modified by the frequency, $x(t)$ is upconverted in frequency to match the central frequency of the APD, $x_{up}(t)$. Then the APD is measured with an APD-measuring receiver to obtain the APD curve; an example of this measurement is shown in Figure 8.

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Figure 6 - Statistical APD calibration diagram.

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Figure 7 - Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) signal pattern.

Figure 8 - APD measure curve of signal pattern.

With $X[n]$, and the APD_{curve} digitalised, we can apply the digital sample processing to extract the statistical parameters of the measurements.

For the APD_{curve} , its cumulative distribution function (CDF) and its probability density function (PDF) are calculated. By using the PDF, an algorithm performs a regeneration of pseudo-random samples, $X_{regen}[n]$, that follow the same distribution as the APD_{curve} , which allows obtaining the statistical parameters of the APD measurement. Fig. 9 presents a comparison of the PDFs for APD_{curve} , $X_{regen}[n]$, and $X_{filtered}[n]$ for a GMM signal pattern. As can be observed, the samples obtained through the regeneration process align perfectly with the others at 40 dBμV and above. Also, this explains why the PDF is slightly different at lower amplitudes.

Figure 9- APD measure curve of Signal Pattern.

On the other hand, since the APD measurement algorithm filters the signal using a band pass filter (BPF) and a low pass filter (LPF), the pseudo-random pattern signal $X[n]$ follow the same process using CISRP 16-1-1 digital filters to obtain an APD equivalent $X_{filtered}[n]$.

Then, using $X_{regen}[n]$ obtained from the APD_{curve} and $X_{filtered}[n]$ from the time domain measurement of the pseudo-random signal pattern generated in base-band, the statistical parameters of both samples are derived and a set of comparisons is performed to calibrate the APD measuring function.

To quantify the statistical differences between the generated pseudo-random pattern signals and the APD curve, three methods have been established.

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Firstly, the statistical parameters—mean, median, variance, skewness, kurtosis, and modes—are compared for $X_{\text{filtered}}[n]$ and $X_{\text{regen}}[n]$. With these values, an accurate quantification of the difference in the statistical characteristics of the calibration samples can be obtained.

Secondly, a measurement is performed comparing the values shared by $X_{\text{regen}}[n]$ and $X_{\text{filtered}}[n]$ taking into account where 95% of the most representative values are found in $X_{\text{filtered}}[n]$ using its CDF. By this calculation a percentage of values within the 95% that $X_{\text{regen}}[n]$ shares with $X_{\text{filtered}}[n]$ is obtained.

Finally, the graphical representation of the amplitude error as a function of probability is obtained by comparing the measured APD subindice curve with a reference APD subindice curve, mathematically defined based on the statistical parameters — amplitude, frequency, and duty cycle — used to generate the initial pattern signals. This representation allows an intuitive assessment of whether the obtained curve is calibrated and compliant with the proposed reliability ranges, as defined by the power level accuracy in the CISPR 16-1-1 standard.

3. Interpreting and presenting the APD calibration results

Calibration results should be presented clearly and understandably. However, when dealing with APD calibration results, this process is not always straightforward. In principle, we have two sets of measured data points that need to be compared to reference values. One set of measured values corresponds to measured power levels, and another set corresponds to measured probability levels. Both measurement sets should be compared to their respective reference-generated values. However, for most probability values, the uncertainty is much smaller than the measured probability itself and can be neglected. In special or limiting cases, when this is not the case, the relevant amplitude levels will be excluded from the final calibration data obtained through the deterministic calibration procedure results.

General calibration results are typically presented in terms of an error function that displays the difference between the measured values obtained by measuring the receiver under calibration and the reference values. The final calibration uncertainty is then a combination of the uncertainty associated with both the receiver measured values and reference values. If we assign the APD measured with receiver under calibration as APD_x and the generated reference APD as APD_s then the error function is defined by (15).

$$e = APD_x - APD_s \tag{15}$$

The results can be displayed on a plot where the horizontal axis represents the error in decibels, and the vertical axis represents the probability level. An ideal example, in which the EUT does not display any deviation from the reference APD, can be seen in Fig.10. This figure also displays the CISPR 16-1-1 limits in terms of level-measurement accuracy.

Figure 10- Ideal error function.

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3.1 “Deterministic calibration” results

The deterministic calibration procedure was applied to a traditional benchtop superheterodyne electromagnetic interference (EMI) receiver. The EMI receiver used was a Rohde & Schwarz ESW8, which was tuned to the central frequency using the same time base as the signal generators. The Measurement was performed with a 1 MHz resolution bandwidth (RBW) and an acquisition time of 120 s. The APD results are shown in Figure 11. The reference signal had the following characteristics:

- $s(t) = CW; f = 1 \text{ GHz}$
- $L_1 = 52 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$
- $w(t) = \text{Pulse modulated CW}; f = 1 \text{ GHz}; \text{width} = 100 \mu\text{s}; \text{period} = 1 \text{ s}; P_2 = 10^{-4}$.
- $L_2 = 107 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$

The measured APD corresponds well to the expected distribution derived from the reference signals, as illustrated in Figure 12, where the results are displayed in terms of the error function and the final measurement uncertainty. The amplitude accuracy specification is confirmed to be compliant in this receiver. At higher probabilities, the EUT measured amplitude deviates by up to 1 dB as we approach the 10^{-4} probability threshold. The uncertainty in the error function also increases in this region; however, after we cross the 10^{-4} threshold, the uncertainty gradually decreases. The main uncertainty contribution below the 10^{-4} probability level is attributed to the noise floor of the APD measurement function on the EUT, since the SNR worsens at lower probabilities, where the signal $w(t)$ is not present.

Figure 11 - APD measurement on the receiver under calibration at 10^{-4} probability threshold.

Figure 12 - Error function with uncertainty for 10^{-4} probability threshold.

To calibrate lower the probability levels, for example at 10^{-6} , a new set of reference signals was set with RF power sensors with the following characteristics:

- $s(t) = CW; f = 1 \text{ GHz}$
- $L_1 = 52 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$
- $w(t) = \text{Pulse modulated CW}; f = 1 \text{ GHz}; \text{width} = 1 \mu\text{s}; \text{period} = 1 \text{ s}; P_2 = 10^{-6}$
- $L_2 = 107 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$

The EUT was tuned to the same frequency as the two signal generators and was connected to the same time base. The acquisition time was again set to 120 s, and a 1 MHz RBW was used. The resulting APD as measured by the receiver under calibration is shown in Fig.13.

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Figure 13 - APD measured on the receiver under calibration at a 10^{-6} probability threshold.

Figure 14 - Error function with uncertainty at a 10^{-6} probability threshold.

When the APD with a lower probability threshold at 10^{-6} is measured with the receiver under calibration, the transition through the probability threshold is not as sharp as in the previous measurement. It can be seen from Fig.14 that the measured amplitude level at 10^{-6} does not equal the level of signal $w(t)$ which is set at $L_2 = 107 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$. The results of this measurement do not comply with CISPR 16-1-1 prescribed limits for amplitude accuracy. The reference signals were subsequently characterised again using a high-frequency oscilloscope to confirm their accuracy and expected values. The reference signals were found to be correct. Afterwards the manufacturer was contacted, and the reason for the discrepancy was determined to be the combination of the chosen measurement time of 120 s together with the 1 MHz RBW and the low power level of the signal $s(t)$.

The manufacturer suggested using a calibration reference signal with different characteristics and an acquisition time of 10 s. The new reference signal characteristics are summarised below.

- $s(t) = CW; f = 1 \text{ GHz}$
- $L_1 = 87 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$
- $w(t) = \text{Pulse modulated CW}; f = 1 \text{ GHz}; \text{width} = 10 \mu\text{s}; \text{period} = 10 \text{ s}; P_2 = 10^{-6}$
- $L_2 = 107 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$

The new acquisition time meant that the uncertainty due to sampling resolution of the measuring receiver under calibration could no longer be neglected. The uncertainty of the measured probability level on the EUT was of the order of $0,5 \times 10^{-6}$. To take this into account amplitude level measurements on the APD around the probability threshold were excluded. The data points that were excluded fell within the probability interval of $10^{-6} \pm 5 \times 10^{-7}$. The results are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. The amplitude accuracy specifications defined in CISPR 16-1-1 were successfully confirmed at the 10^{-6} probability level.

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Figure 15 - APD measured on the receiver under calibration at a 10^{-6} probability threshold.

Figure 16 - Error function with uncertainty at a 10^{-6} probability threshold.

3.2 “Statistical calibration” results

This section presents the results from the statistical APD calibration process using the WGN and GMM reference signals.

A straightforward approach to visualising the error in the APD measurements (APD_{curve}) is by comparing the acquired data with a simulated reference derived from known statistical parameters ($APD_{pattern}$). Nevertheless, such representation has limited significance for calibration purposes unless the maximum permissible deviation boundaries, within which the APD_{curve} is expected to lie, are explicitly specified. The fixed limits of ± 2.7 dB are taken from CISPR 16-1-1, which defines the power level accuracy requirement.

Fig. 17 illustrates the corresponding error margins for P0 WGN (a) and P1 GMM (b) reference signals. As can be observed, both measurements exhibit an APD_{curve} that is contained within the confidence margins derived from the $APD_{pattern}$ representation. Nevertheless, these plots do not provide meaningful calibration insights in the regions where the APD probability remains flat, such as the range between 40-75 dB μ V in Fig.17a, and between 40–55 dB μ V and 80–90 dB μ V in Fig.17b. To address this limitation, an alternative method for representing measurement error is presented.

Figure 17 APD Error Margins for P0 WGN (a) and P1 GMM (b)

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The alternative representation, similar to the one presented in the deterministic calibration, provides a clear visualisation of the measurement error even within amplitude regions where the probability of exceeding the threshold remains flat. To achieve this, the difference between APD_{curve} and $APD_{pattern}$ is computed according to (16).

$$e(\text{dB}) = APD_{curve}(\text{dB}\mu\text{V}) - APD_{pattern}(\text{dB}\mu\text{V}) \quad (16)$$

For this calculation, only the samples with the highest amplitude threshold for a given probability level are considered. In this way, a plot is obtained where the horizontal axis represents the amplitude error corresponding to each probability value on the vertical axis derived from APD_{curve} .

Fig. 18, which presents the APD error for the WGN reference signal, clearly illustrates how the error magnitude increases as the probability decreases. However, the observed deviations are of the order of 1-2 dB and remain within the proposed limits. This effect occurs because, at higher amplitude thresholds, the probability of exceeding the threshold is lower, resulting in greater measurement uncertainty. Detecting values at such low probabilities is inherently arbitrary and complicates compliance with the CISPR 16-1-1 standard, as it requires APD measurements with a minimum probability of 10^{-7} . Achieving such low-probability levels demands either a very large number of samples or extended acquisition times. This requirement is one of the main criticisms directed at the APD measurement method and its associated standard.

Figure 18 - Statistic Calibration Amplitude Error of (P0).

This requirement is one of the main criticisms directed at the APD measurement method and its associated standard. Figure 19 illustrates the error associated with the GMM reference signals.

Three distinct effects can be identified. The first is a systematic offset observed at high probability levels of approximately 0.5 dB in magnitude. This offset is consistently present across all measurements until the second mode of the GMM is reached, in the APD curve, this is represented as the second flat section.

The second effect is an increase in error variability when the second mode of the GMM appears. For all GMM patterns with different duty cycles, an abrupt transition in the APD error is observed when this condition is reached. This phenomenon arises because, at a given probability level, the likelihood of a discrepancy between simulated and measured amplitudes increases, leading to larger errors.

The third effect is that as the probability decreases, the error becomes less consistent and more erratic. This behaviour aligns with the observed APD error in the WGN reference and is attributed to the inherent measurement uncertainty at such low probability levels.

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Figure 19 Statistic Calibration Amplitude Error of P1 (a), P2 (b), P3 (c), P4 (d).

In addition to the error representation for the statistical calibration of the APD, a metric has been defined to compare the shared values between the signals X_{regen} and X_{filtered} . The measure considers where 95% of the most representative values are found in X_{filtered} using its CDF. By this calculation, a percentage of values within the 95% that X_{regen} shares with X_{filtered} is obtained. Table. I show the results of this measure for the pattern signals. Considering that the maximum achievable value for this test is 95%, and that the most deviating result corresponds to 94.84% for P4 reference signal, it can be concluded that the APD is appropriately calibrated with respect to this metric.

Table I - 95% Proportion test.

APD measure	P0	P1	P2	P3	P4
Standard	94.85%	94.98%	94.91%	94.86%	94.84%

Finally, a comparison has been conducted between the statistical parameters used to generate the WGN and GMM references and those obtained from X_{regen} . Table. II presents the results of this comparison, which exhibit a minimal error; thus, it can be concluded that the APD measuring receiver has not significantly altered the signal. Therefore, the resulting APD curve is considered to be correctly calibrated.

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Table II - Statistical parameters error.

Statistics	P0	P1	P2	P3	P4
Average	-0.03	-0.05	-0.03	-0.03	-0.03
Median	-0.03	-0.04	-0.03	-0.03	-0.03
Variance	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09
Skewness	-0.02	-0.01	-0.02	-0.11	-0.03
Kurtosis	0.20	0.02	0.01	0.21	0.21
Mode 1	-	-0.49	0.07	-0.20	-0.24
Mode 1	-	0.15	-1.31	0.59	-

4. Conclusions

This document discusses calibration methods for the APD function in measuring receivers, combining deterministic and statistical procedures to ensure a comprehensive validation of the APD reliability.

The proposed deterministic calibration method utilises continuous and pulsed signals with precisely controlled parameters to validate the APD curve. In contrast, the statistical calibration approach employs pseudo-random stochastic reference signals with known statistical properties to assess APD measurement errors under more realistic electromagnetic conditions.

Experimental results have shown that the measurement uncertainties for the APD remain below the ± 2.7 dB power level accuracy limit, established by the CISPR 16-1-1 standard, for APD detectors.

In conclusion, Deliverable 8 of EMC-STD project has been successfully achieved and this document meets the objective 4 requirements committed in Annex 1 JRP Protocol.

5. References

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